

Investigation on Magnetic Structure for transition metal difluorides of NiF_2

P.Sivaprakash, S.Arumugam*

*Centre for High Pressure Research, School of Physics, Bharathidasan University,
Tiruchirappalli, India – 620 024.*

*Corresponding Author: sarumugam1963@yahoo.com

NiF_2 is one of the interesting candidates from the family of complex non-oxide functional materials namely transition metal (TM) fluorides (MF_2 ($M = \text{Ni, Fe, Mn, Co}$)). Its exotic properties are advantageous towards electric and magnetic applications. The tetragonal unit cell consists of two formula units with two M atoms in the unit cell, one at corner of the cell and another at body diagonal position. The Ni^{2+} ions at the corners and body centers of the unit cell forming two opposed sub lattice with the spins along the c - axis and the spins are tilted away from c - axis by ~ 10 degrees. Its tetragonal structure which goes below $T_N = 71.3$ K in to AFM state with weak FM state. Paul A Fleury (1969) reported the observation of magnetic light scattering in NiF_2 in both its anti-ferromagnetic and paramagnetic phase. The refined structure of NiF_2 is tetragonal structure which belongs to rutile type crystal structure. This study explore that NiF_2 exhibit anti-ferromagnetic phase at the transition point if $T_N = 68.5$ K and weak ferromagnetic transition occurs below that temperature. This present results enrich the understanding of the structural and magnetic behaviour of NiF_2 transition metal difluoride.

References:

1. L. Neel, Ann. phys. 5, . 256 (1936).
2. J. H. Van Vleck, J. Chem. Phys. 9, 85 (1941).
3. H. Bizette and B. Tsai, Compt. rend. 209, 205 (1939).
4. H. Bizette and B. Tsai, Compt. rend. 212, 119 (1941).